

Development of a methodology to define data-driven and measurement-based services for the Built Environment

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Abstract— This paper describes a methodology to define how high-quality data collection and usage can be exploited to develop data-driven and measurement-based services that fit the requirements of the Built Environment (BE) stakeholders. Given the increasing innovation that the BE is undergoing, the need of services based on data is required. This implies the development of tailored sensors networks and measurement techniques which aims at guaranteeing the quality of data to deliver efficient and digitalized solutions. The key role played by stakeholders led to the implementation of a co-creation approach for the identification of stakeholders' specific requests. Their direct involvement in the process has been crucial to extract data-driven and measurement-based services from their perspective, such as the development of Digital Twin, services for enhanced comfort and wellbeing and services for data-quality monitoring. The outcome of this research highlights that stakeholders' common target is a digitalized BE where IoT sensor networks and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques work together to guarantee the effectiveness and the high-quality of the services that may be delivered for BE innovation.

Keywords—Built environment, digitalization, IoT devices, data-driven service, sensor network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Measurement of physical quantities plays a pivotal role in the design and development of innovative digitalized services for the Built Environment (BE). In particular, the metrology is fundamental to define the measurement procedure design of physical quantities that includes the choice of sensors and sensor network, the calibration system, the uncertainty analysis and the decision making procedure. Considering these aspects of metrology, it is possible to increase the high-quality of the data collected within the BE and, as a consequence, develop tailored services for citizens [1]. In this

context, digitalized services for the BE are related to provide a comfortable and functional environment for the occupant [2]. BE concept encloses both the design and management of different categories of buildings (residential, industrial, commercial etc.) and it has been under the spotlight of energy and environmental debates given the urgent need of reducing gas emissions in the building life-cycle [2][3]. The BE is the focus of stakeholders with different interests and needs, who exploit data measured from the BE for different purposes. Hence, an inclusive environment for stakeholders with heterogeneous knowledge and co-creative approach should be applied to ensure the development of a sustainable BE. This also implies the design of innovative approaches that can contribute to the improvement of the indoor and outdoor environmental quality, and to the proactiveness of infrastructures for increased occupants' comfort and customized data-driven services [2]

Nowadays, Internet of Things (IoT) sensors networks and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques work in synergy to improve energy efficiency and the occupant' satisfaction with the surrounding BE [4]. This technological progress should guarantee a radical change in those aspects related to people's interaction with the BE in order to better manage the surroundings and also conduct business. This relies on the deployment of a plethora of smart devices that works and communicates both with the users and among themselves in order to provide smart services, using the measured data [5]. Hence, the increasing innovation that has emerged in the field of smart technologies and also the essential request for a sustainable BE, are encouraging the BE digitalization. Indeed, BE can be considered a relevant source of heterogeneous data, that can be analyzed and processed to develop innovative services for buildings. These services are focused on various themes: occupants' wellbeing and comfort, carbon footprint

reduction, and improvement of energy efficiency of buildings [4]. They are typically developed in association with a great amount of data collected by spread IoT sensor networks. For instance, the possibility of measuring comfort, which is a quantity that relies on multiple variables, measured through various sensors networks, opens the possibility to develop and exploit data-driven services that guarantee human comfort in the BE [6], [7], [8]. The usage of data, measured through sensor networks, also introduces the importance of studying how data may be affected by measurement uncertainty, low data quality and missing data. Thus, the introduction of a metrological approach for guaranteeing high-data quality and the application of advanced measurement procedure is pivotal to deliver efficient data-driven services.

In this context, the DigiBUILD project - High-Quality Data-Driven Services for a Digital Built Environment towards a Climate-Neutral Building Stock - fits the continuous developments that the BE is undergoing, through the emerging new technologies and techniques such as the introduction of IoT sensors in indoor spaces and the implementation of AI-based approaches for managing and forecasting energy consumptions and related costs. DigiBUILD project is funded by the European Union in the framework of Horizon Europe program and aims at developing an infrastructure where traditional silos approaches could be replaced by digital and smart buildings, merging heterogeneous data sources, and giving the stakeholders a central role in these buildings by making use of high-quality data and next generation digital building services. Their targets are energy efficiency, energy costs reduction, comfort and wellbeing maintenance and building digitalization. These topics will be handled through the implementation of a digital platform which matches the technological innovation acting within the BE. This implies the development of a Digital Twin of the involved buildings to guarantee energy efficiency and costs reduction. The development of such technology triggers the need of collecting high quantities of data and the installation of suitable sensor networks.

A crucial step for the deployment of digitalization services relies on the proper identification of the final end-users and of their needs. Therefore, the concept of co-creation has a relevant influence on the final result. Indeed, the co-creation approach can be used to open the direct dialogue with the stakeholders and to retrieve directly from them the basis for the development of technological services for the digitalization of BE.

In the light of this, the aim of the current study is the development of a methodology for the definition of high-quality data-driven services, in the framework of the BE digitalization. The developed approach is user-centered since the importance of stakeholders is pivotal to understand the needs of the BE. In addition, the proposed methodology tries to provide the practical step for a measurement procedure that involves sensor networks and AI-based techniques whose target is guaranteeing and monitoring the quality of data which need to be exploitable for the development of the requested services. The questions that this research tries to answer are “Which services are needed by the stakeholders for the digitalization of a Built Environment?”, “How technology can support the deployment of a high-quality data-driven BE?”.

The application of the strategy proposed in this paper is the solution to these questions. In fact, the proposed

methodology tries to satisfy the emerging need of services which are based on high-quality data. The level of quality that data should have to guarantee a successful deployment of the services has to be supported by efficient measurement techniques and setups.

Hence, the present work highlights the importance of designing a methodology to deliver high quality data-driven services, which underlines the key role of the measurement process that has to be included in the BE framework to assess data quality and guarantee the deployment of efficient technological services that satisfy the requests of the stakeholders in the BE scenario.

II. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology [9] developed for the identification of data-driven services for BE digitalization tailored to the requests of the stakeholders included in this field (Fig. 1). For this purpose, a co-creation approach was developed. It encourages the synergy between people with different backgrounds who work to accomplish a common goal. Specifically, this methodology aims at obtaining relevant insights that are exploitable in the BE digitalization context starting from a deep knowledge of higher-level information (user needs). In other words, the practical steps described in this section are the activities that should be developed to initiate the process for digitalizing the BE. This approach has been developed by defining and identifying the relevant data and scenarios preferable by the stakeholders, including data sources (e.g., through user requirements).

Fig. 1 shows the different stages included in this process. It allowed the passage from the high-level information represented by the user needs to the more detailed information at the base of service definition. In particular, the designed methodology included the following activities (Fig. 1):

- 1) User stories definition.
- 2) User requirements extraction.
- 3) Service definition.

A. Stakeholders

The proposed strategy is based on co-creation (Fig. 1) where it is crucial to establish a direct interaction with the stakeholders to identify their needs. Hence, this section reports all the end-users that have been involved in the design of the BE digitalization services.

37 different stakeholders have been recruited and involved in the interviews process. These participants can be grouped in the following categories:

- Facility manager (i.e., office building manager, property manager, District Heating Network (DHN) manager, head of site operation);
- Municipality and policy maker;
- Sustainability stakeholder (i.e., sustainability manager, sustainability expert, responsible for Environmental, social, governance (ESG) target, responsible for carbon zero targets);
- Occupants;
- Experts (i.e., data solution architect, expert in building services);

Figure 1. Schematization of the methodology applied for the definition of the high-quality data-driven services for built environment digitalization.

- Investors.

B. User stories definition

The first stage of the proposed strategy is focused on the collection of high-level information concerning the stakeholders' needs (Fig. 1). In particular, they are the user stories which suggest what the end-user desires and the reason. To accomplish this goal, firstly the potential stakeholders have been identified. Then, interview-based meetings have been organized.

C. User requirements extraction

The extraction of the user stories has triggered the development of the next steps. Indeed, once all the stakeholders' needs have been highlighted, the core of the co-creation approach presented in this paper has been accomplished. The target now is the extraction of user requirements (Fig. 1) by establishing a direct dialogue with the stakeholders. Hence, a second round of interviews has been implemented by organizing 9 workshops where the stakeholders have been asked more technical questions related to the previously mentioned user stories.

D. Service Definition

The clear identification of the stakeholders and the collection of their needs according to the applied interview-based approach, led to the designing of data-driven services focused on the digitalization of BE. These services have been created starting from the requests of the end-users and their coherence with the digitalization process that BE should undergo.

III. OUTCOMES

The first outcome of this study is the methodology itself (Fig. 1). Indeed, the current work has provided a strategy for the settlement of high-quality data services for the practical

implementation for building digitalization. From the extracted user requirements, it has been possible to individuate common functionalities that stakeholders expect to trigger the digitalization of the BE.

The co-creation methodology proposed in the current work has identified the main categories of targets for stakeholders interested in the digitalization of BE. In particular, the end-users in this field are focused on:

- *Installation IoT smart sensors and devices.* Insights of the interviews showed that many buildings still are not provided with smart sensors for environmental monitoring, e.g., smart meters that can measure and collect energy data. For this reason, stakeholders have highlighted the need to include new devices in the measurement process. This is the preliminary step for the development of data-driven services.
- *Energy performance monitoring, benchmarking and prediction.* The interviewed stakeholders have been highly concerned about the monitoring of energy performance to verify the quality of the building by applying also AI-based forecasting system focused on the prediction of energy consumptions and costs. These aspects are considered as favorable steps toward a digitalized BE since they can lead to an energy system with lower costs and higher efficiency.
- *Enhanced comfort and well-being.* The participants have pointed out their interest in maintaining comfort in indoor environments. Indeed, services for comfort monitoring to guarantee people wellbeing are needed. The application of this need into a BE can be translated into a service which provides networks of IoT devices for the measurement of specific data (e.g., environmental data, Indoor Environmental Quality data etc.) and the

implementation of AI-based approaches for the quantification of this human-centered factor (e.g., thermal comfort, visual comfort etc.).

- *Development of Digital Twins for designing future buildings and for managing their energy efficiency.* In particular, the stakeholders require a digital tool that displays an overview of the building which considers the installed sensors and the building systems such as the HVAC system. The proposed digital tool may provide also a forecasting section where energy efficiency, energy costs and comfort predictions can be displayed to the end-users.
- *Data Quality monitoring* through the implementation of specific factors such as accuracy, reliability, consistency, completeness, relevance. Indeed, BE digitalization implies big data collection, thus one of the services emerged from the interviews is measuring and monitoring their quality with the computation of specific factors in order to guarantee accurate data assessments and an efficient smart BE.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The aim of the current work is to provide an effective methodology for defining how the measurement of high-quality data through digitalized sensor networks and AI-based techniques can support the development of services which fit the need of stakeholders in the BE.

In this context, the direct interaction with the stakeholders is the key point for proper identification and an effective deployment of data-driven services as requested by the technological progress that BE is undergoing. Hence, the application of a co-creation approach has been crucial in this work for the extraction of the stakeholders' needs. In fact, from the activities developed in the framework of this paper, the resulting services are strictly compliant with the digitalization process that BE is undergoing.

In particular, the stakeholders' requests imply the installation of new devices which are mainly IoT and smart sensors to collect and provide high-quality data. Consequently, one main focus that emerged from the defined services is the development of services for quantification and monitoring of data quality. For instance, for the service dedicated to comfort and well-being, the comfort monitoring process must guarantee the collection of high-quality data and the application of AI techniques to provide accurate results. Moreover, from the co-creation activities stakeholders asked for a specific service which is exclusively dedicated to data quality measurement. This service should provide objective factors (e.g., accuracy, completeness, consistency etc.) that support the development and delivery of a high-quality digitalized BE.

The category of devices required by the stakeholders matches the increasing need of introducing AI-based models in the BE context. AI can be exploited for forecasting and monitoring energy consumption and costs to provide a product that support stakeholders from an economic and consumption point of view. The AI-based service may encourage investments on new technologies to guarantee costs reduction for high quality energy service. This reasoning is also linked

to the maintenance and monitoring of IEQ in working facilities or residential buildings (BE). Indeed, this request should be coupled with the issues raised before: energy efficiency and costs reduction. The end-user asks for a tradeoff between the maintenance of comfort and energy consumptions.

In conclusion, the proposed methodology underlines the pivotal role that IoT sensors and innovative measurement techniques have in the BE context to guarantee high-quality data collection and the effective deployment of data-driven services. Moreover, the current work has succeeded in providing the practical steps (Fig. 1) for the definition of data-driven services which are both user-centered since strictly related to the stakeholders' requests, but also measurement-based given the deep renovation process that is revolutionizing the BE scenarios through the application of digitalized metrological approaches.

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